

Impact of teaching strategies that teachers employ on students' level of motivation to learn effectively

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16760524>

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of teaching strategies on students' motivation to learn effectively. It begins by acknowledging the multifaceted nature of learning, influenced by the learner's environment, emotional state, intelligence, and teaching strategies. Emphasis is placed on the critical role that motivation—both intrinsic and extrinsic—plays in facilitating effective learning. The study identifies key factors, such as a safe classroom atmosphere, emotionally supportive teaching, and diverse instructional methods, as essential to enhancing learner engagement. Drawing on the perspectives of various scholars, the literature review further supports the argument that motivation acts as a catalyst for academic success and behavioral transformation in learners. The primary aim is to examine how different teaching strategies affect motivation and consequently lead to effective learning, while also identifying best practices to make students more self-directed. Through this, the study seeks to inform educators on the importance of adopting motivational teaching strategies for optimal learning outcomes.

Keywords: Motivation, Teaching Strategies, Intrinsic Motivation, Extrinsic Motivation, Effective Learning, Student Engagement, Classroom Environment, Learner-Centered Teaching, Emotional Safety, Self-Directed Learning

Introduction

'Introduction' presents statement of the problem, purpose of the study, research objectives and research questions. This chapter in stating the problem it elaborates on the different ways people learn as a learner. It also brings into limelight how environment, associations with friends, different capacity and ability of the learners, the use of teaching aids in the classroom, intelligences of the learners, teaching strategies and emotional state of the learners contributes to learning. Most important of all, it discusses at length about impact of teaching strategies that teachers employ on students' level motivation to learn and results in effective learning in our learners. This chapter concludes with a brief summary.

Statement of the Problem

Learning is a continuous process that never ends either with age or with time. Hammond (2003) [26] states that, our brain plays an important role in learning. The way learning environment is constructed makes a difference and learning is also based on the associations or connections we make with the surroundings and environment that we live in.

Learning occurs in particular social and cultural environment, and finally the different ways people think and feel about their own learning affects their development as learners.

Although above mentioned ways contributed to learning, even motivation to learn contributed to learning so that learning becomes effective. My points of view on learning is supported by Hammond (2003) [26] stating that learning involves both internal (mental) developmental and external interactions with the environment. "People learn by making sense of environment and stimuli around them," (Hammond, 2003, p.16) [26].

Emotionally safe classroom too contributed to my learning. It refers to the mood and flow of the classroom as the lesson begins, during the lesson and ends. Roeser, Eccles and Sameroff (2000, as cited in Hammond, 2003) [26] state that an emotionally safe classroom environment is necessary for students' cognitive learning, growth and creative expressions. Even Probst (1984) [31] asserts that teaching atmosphere in classroom should be non-threatening, conducive, non-competitive and thought-provoking thus allowing students to enjoy the lesson taught. Moreover,

(1996, cited in Hammond, 2003) ^[26] also state that our emotional state has the potential to influence our thinking. Our students learn and perform more successfully when they feel secure, happy and excited about the subject matter. Researcher learnt that as teachers we need to possess these motivational skills, since motivation makes our students eager, receptive of what is being taught, makes more responsible in life such as in making decision in life. Wilson, Robeck and Michael (1974, cited in Burden, 2000) ^[10] state that if students can be motivated, they can be taught. If not, school work is a burden to them and as well as to the teacher. The motivated learners become self-directing.

Purpose of study

Factors such as: environment, teaching strategies, intelligence and emotion as mentioned above makes our learners motivated while learning and consequently affects in effective learning in our learners. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to find out impact of teaching strategies that our teachers employ raise students' level of motivation to learn effectively in the school. I feel that the real task of a teacher is to transform the learners and make them responsible in life rather than transmitting the knowledge and the content of the subject.

Objectives

Following objectives were identified for the study:

1. To find out what actual teaching strategies are being used in the classroom.
2. To unfold how using different teaching strategies raise motivational level of our learners resulting in effective learning.
3. To determine student behavioral changes in the motivated teaching-learning classroom through classroom observation.

Research Question

Impact of teaching strategies that teachers employ on students' level of motivation to learn effectively.

Sub Question

In seeking answers to the question, the researcher employed these sub-questions:

1. What are the different teaching strategies commonly used by teachers in teaching?
2. What can we do as teachers to make our students self-directing?
3. What are the factors that affect learning in students?
4. What teaching strategies can be used to make student learn effectively?
5. How can we motivate our students to learn effectively?

Summary

This chapter has introduced the study problem and setting. It also presented the importance of motivation which is the main driving force behind learning effectively. Kinds of motivation and level of motivation also attributes to the quality of the learning that takes place in the students in the teaching learning process. These triggered the researcher to explore further into the topic. To validate the study, researcher has looked at the different findings and the study

carried out earlier by different authors around the world on motivation and how to motivate learners to learn effectively. Various literatures have been referred and suggestions sought. So the next chapter on literature review discusses these in some depth.

Chapter Two Literature Review

Introduction

Although many educational reforms have been brought in the education system in our country, but I felt the lack of motivational skills and strategies into our curriculum that would support and enhance learning in our classroom settings. Renchler (1992) ^[33] puts forward his findings, affirming that educational motivation have placed many school leaders in a difficult position. Much of the research indicates that our present instructional practices tend to diminish motivation for academic achievement rather than increase it.

So researcher really felt the need and importance of understanding what motivation is? How does motivation help in learning? How we as teacher can motivate our learners to learn effectively. These are some of the questions addressed by literatures review in this chapter.

Definition of Motivation

Motivation is an abstract, hypothetical concept that we use to explain why people think and behave as they do. States that motivation by definition concerns both of these direction and magnitude (intensity). Therefore, motivation explains why people decide to do something, how hard we are going to pursue it and how long we are willing to sustain the activity. So motivation is the greatest unseen force or drive that prevails within us and makes us strive for and work to achieve something.

Student's behavior in the motivated teaching-learning classroom

Motivation is an important factor that facilitates to accomplish quality learning. Similarly, Wlodkowski (1984) ^[42] states that motivation is used to describe those processes that can arouse and initiate behavior, gives direction and purpose to behavior, continue to allow behavior to persist, and lead to choosing or preferring a particular behavior. Motivation provides the gusto and direction in doing something to achieve something. From it, we know that the motivated learners become self-regulated and bring behavior changes. Corno and Rohrkemper (1985) ^[15] state that self-regulation of cognition and behavior is an important aspect of student learning and academic performance in the classroom context.

Hammond (2003) ^[26] states that motivation to learn is usually associated with an eagerness to learn and a commitment to learning. Students who are motivated to learn can be observed working thoroughly on the task, seeking understanding and persevering when they encounter challenges. Also willingness to think through problems and work through challenges to achieve mastery of a concept or skill goes beyond simply having fun during learning. In the same vein, Stipek (2002) ^[39] states that for students to learn and derive maximum benefits from the school, educators must provide a learning context in which students are

motivated to engage actively and productively in the activities. Theobald (2006) ^[40] says that the greatest challenge of teachers in the 21st century is to provide an environment and atmosphere that can stimulate a student's desire to learn. Therefore, to be an effective teacher we must continually seek ways to manipulate the learning environment in order to maximize the motivational levels of individual students to learn effectively. Through literature, researcher has come to learn two types of motivation and various motivational theories.

Types of Motivation

Literature classifies motivation into two broad categories. Even Burden (2000) ^[10] in his book, 'Powerful Classroom Management Strategies,' talks of having two broad categories of motivation-intrinsic and extrinsic.

Intrinsic motivation

Burden (2000) ^[10] states that intrinsic motivation is a response to needs that exists within the student, such as curiosity, the need to know, and feelings of competence or growth. Also intrinsic motivation may involve the internal satisfaction that the student feels when performing the task. We have situations in which the source of motivation lies inside the task. In such cases we work because the task itself is interesting and does not require any external source of motivation. This situation represents intrinsic motivation such as a child's play, reading an interesting novel, writing a poem or a story. Intrinsic motivation refers to motivation that is driven by an interest or enjoyment in the task itself, and exists within the individual rather than relying on any external pressure. Sansone and Harackiewicz (2000) ^[35] state that when individuals are intrinsically motivated, they engage in an activity because they are interested in and enjoy the activity. This intrinsic motivation plays a vital role in effective learning of our learners in the school as well as it supports my research topic on "Impact of teaching strategies that teachers employ on students' level of motivational to learn effectively."

Extrinsic motivation

On the other hand, Burden (2000) ^[10], states that extrinsic motivation refers to motivation that comes from outside the learner and involves the delivery of external rewards when a student completes a task. The reward might be words of praise from the teacher, a high grade, or a privilege. Undertaking a given task may be motivated by promise of a prize or some other kind of gain which is external to the task. Thus, the task is instrumental in receiving or gaining access to the external reward. Further in line with Burden (2000) ^[10], Sansone and Harackiewicz (2000) ^[35] state that extrinsically motivated individuals engage in activities for instrumental or other reasons such as receiving a reward. In all, such situations the locus of control is external to the person who is asked to undertake the activity. Such situations characterize the extrinsic motivation.

Summary

Motivation is fundamental to life, and indeed most likely the self as agent evolved to facilitate the goal pursuits associated with crucial motivations. Motivation is relevant and very important in learning as a learner because learning

is an active process requiring conscious and deliberate activity. So I have discussed in detail about the motivation. In the following chapter I would be looking at the methodology that has been employed while carrying out the study.

Chapter: Three Research Methodology

Introduction

Methodology is the plan or proposal to conduct the research. It entails discussion of philosophical assumption, strategies of inquiry, worldviews, the tools that would be employed in the research and how the research would be carried out in the field. This chapter presents each of these in some depth.

Philosophical Assumption

In carrying out the research work, researcher follows certain philosophical assumptions. So to conduct my research studies will be based on the philosophical assumption epistemological. I base my studies on this philosophical assumption, since in this assumption researcher tries to get as close as possible to the participants being studied and gets the first-hand experience from the participants.

Research Paradigms or Worldviews

Guba (1990, cited in Creswell, 2007) ^[17], states that a paradigm or worldviews is a set of beliefs that guide action. My research aligns with the social constructivism since the researcher here tried to understand the world they live in and work. Here they try to make meaning of their experience. Creswell (2007) ^[17] says that the goal of research then, is to rely as much as possible on the participants' views of the situation. My research was based on the principle of constructivist knowledge claim which believes that human beings construct meanings as they interact and interpret their experiences.

Research Approach

In the world of research there are three approaches that are used by the researchers to research. I am a novice researcher and a beginner in the field of research. So, the method used in my research was qualitative approach since I am more familiar with it. Creswell (2009) ^[18] defines saying that this approach is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or group ascribe to a social or human problem. At the same time Creswell (2009) ^[18] states that the process of research involves emerging questions and procedures, data typically collected in the participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particular to general themes, and the researchers making interpretations of the meaning of the data.

The qualitative approach uses the descriptive and explorative nature of research for the study. Even the nature of the research question is very simple. Creswell (2007) ^[17] succinctly puts forward stating that qualitative research questions are open-ended, evolving, and non-directional. It restates the purpose of the study in more specific terms. It starts with a word such as 'how' and 'what' rather than 'why'; and is few in numbers. These are the characteristics of qualitative research. Therefore, I applied this approach in my research since, I am familiar with it. So, my research topic involved conducting the study in the natural everyday

setting in the school and developing meanings of the experiences of the teachers and the students. Therefore, qualitative research approach was found to be the most appropriate to conduct my study.

Qualitative Research Design

In conducting qualitative research, my study topic aligned with phenomenological study because it dealt with the study of human behavior or human experience in relation to a particular situation which the participants have experienced. Researcher carried out research from a phenomenological perspective because “a phenomenological study describes the meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or a phenomenon” (Creswell, 2007, p.57) [17]. Bogdan and Biklen (1992) [6] further adds stating that researcher in the phenomenological mode attempts to understand the meaning of events and interactions to ordinary people in particular situation. Similarly, Douglas (1976) [21] maintains that phenomenologist do not assume they know what things mean to the people they are studying.

Research Tools

In conducting qualitative research, as a novice researcher, I preferred to employ participant observation and semi-structured interview as the main tools to collect information from the participants.

Interviews

“Interview is one of the main data collection tools in qualitative research,” Punch (2005, p.168) [32]. Punch (2005, p.168) [32] further states, “It is a very good way of accessing people’s perception, meanings, definition of situations and constructions of reality.” Also interview is the one of the most powerful ways of understanding others. The use of semi-structured interview allows the researcher to control over the line of questioning (Creswell, 2009) [18]. Even Bogdan and Biklen (1992) [6] support the use of this tool in my research saying that with semi-structured interviews you are confident of getting comparable data across subjects. Therefore, Researcher in this study used the semi-structured interview.

According to Foster (1996, cited in Punch, 2005, p.178) [32], “Observation has been extensively used by psychologists and even by educational researchers.” In observation researcher’s role is known to the participants. Further Punch (2005, p.179) [32] states, “Observation includes listening as well as looking, and everyday face to face interaction depends heavily on both verbal and visual behavior.” In observation researcher has a first-hand experience as well as it has advantages.

Study Site

The research sites for my study would be: Mongar Higher Secondary School, Mongar Middle Secondary School and Kidheykhar Central School, Mongar. These three schools would be used in data collection during my research period, since researcher work in one of the school and other two schools are located just nearby. It would be very convenient.

Participant Sampling

In the study, researcher would invite teachers and students

keeping in mind the gender issues too. I would do purposive sampling since I would choose them as per their experience in the field of study and those who could articulate their experiences well. Creswell (2007, p.119) [17] succinctly states, “Most importantly, they must be individuals who have experienced the phenomenon being explored and can articulate their lived experiences.”

Interviewing Process

Researcher would interview participant one-on-one and would use laptop recorder to record the information. Eisner (1991, p 183) [22] believes, “...conducting a good interview is, in some way, like participating in a good conversation: listening intently and asking questions that focus on concrete examples and feelings...” As presented earlier, researcher designed semi-structured questions for the interview and at the time of the interviews I asked related questions to further probe wherever necessary.

Observation Process

Observation would focus on the classroom teaching and learning process. Researcher would observe teachers’ teaching and its impact on the learners. Also look at the impact of teaching strategy that teachers employ in the classroom teaching raises students’ level of motivation to learn effectively. Researcher would observe the expressions of learners, gestures, behavior while teaching would go on. From it researcher would have first-hand experience with the participants as cited by Creswell (2009, p.179) [18], “Researcher can have first-hand experience with the participants as well as record information as it occurs.”

Data Analysis

Creswell (2007, p.148) [17] states, “Data analysis in qualitative research consists of preparing and organizing the data for analysis, then reducing the data into themes through a process of coding and condensing the codes, and finally representing the data in figures, tables, or a discussion.” It was just interpreting and making sense out of the collected materials. Bogdan and Biklen (1998, p 157) [7] state, “Data analysis is the process of systematically searching and arranging the interview transcripts, field notes, and other materials that you accumulate to increase your own understanding of them and to enable you to present what you have discovered to others.”

The responses from different people on common questions would be grouped together under the same question. Researcher would use same steps and ideas given by Creswell (2007, p. 159) [17] for data analysis. Researcher would fully describe about personal experience with the phenomenon mainly focusing on participants in the study under observation. Then separate the statement and group them into larger unit information, called “main themes” and assign code as per their concept of phenomenon. Thereafter, researcher would write a description of “how” the experience happened. This is called the “structural description,” and researcher would reflect on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, researcher wrote a composite description of the phenomenon both the textual and structural descriptions. This passage is the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspects of a phenomenological

study. It is here that researcher would make an interpretation or meaning of the data being collected from the field as per “what” the participants experienced with the phenomenon and “how” they experienced it (the context).

Validity and Reliability

Best and Kahn (2006, p.403) [5] define, “Validity is an important element for effective research.” Further state, “In qualitative research, validity is the degree to which the qualitative data we collect accurately gauge what we are trying to measure.” It talks of the considerations such as trustworthiness; descriptive, interpretive, theoretical and evaluative are being possessed by the research to qualify for a quality research. According to Best and Kahn (2006) [5] state that trustworthiness concerns addressing the credibility, transferability, so forth of the studies. So different credibility was taken care in the study by interpreting the data as per what participants had to say.

Reliability refers to an act whether or not it is consistent. Burns (2000) [11], Best and Kahn (2006) [5] and Gay, *et al.* (2006) [24] state that a set of terminology include accuracy, stability, dependability and predictability. Reliability basically talks of the consistency of the findings over the time. Gay *et al.*, (2006) [24] describe the reliability and appropriateness of the techniques, be interviews, or observation.

According to Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2007, p. 141) [13]: “triangulation is defined as the use of two or more methods of data collection in the study of some aspects of human behavior.” Since, triangulation is a powerful way of demonstrating concurrent validity, particularly in qualitative research, the same information derived as findings from multiple sources of data will be valid. Therefore, validity and reliability of the study will be ensured.

Research Ethical Issues

Ethical issues are considered to be the most important morality of the researcher in the field of research. Punch (2005, p.276) [32] states, “All social research involves ethical issues.” Bogdan and Biklen (1992) [6] maintain that most academic specialties and professions have code of ethics that set forth these rules. Finally, researcher did maintain the confidentiality of the interviewees and the schools that participated in the study.

Summary

This chapter, “Methodology” introduces the basic requirements of the data analysis. It further presented all the components of a good research project and its importance of having it. So next chapter on Data presentation, Analysis and Discussion will be discussed in more detail of what participants have to say on the research.

Chapter Four

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion

Introduction

This chapter presents the data, its analysis and discussion achieved from the field by conducting interview and observation. The chapter entails main themes namely: ways of teaching, teacher’s preference over the teaching strategies, student’s preference on the teaching strategies, best teaching strategy from student’s perspective, factors

affecting the effective teaching in the classroom, impact of teaching strategies on motivation and what motivates students to learn. The chapter concludes with a brief summary.

Research Setting

Research was conducted in three schools in Mongar Dzongkhag. All participating schools had three teachers and three students each as research participants totaling to eighteen participants.

A: Teacher’s preference of teaching strategies

The data reveal that the teacher participants prefer lecture method, discussion, chalk and talk method, demonstration method, presentation method, and question and answer method. Within these strategies they favor lecture method the most and the reasons reported for such preference include: nature of subjects, Science, Mathematics and even History too which fall under the lecture method demands lots of explanation. For instance, T₃ stated, “Face to face lecturing and demonstrating by chalk and board their mind must be there and it is more effective.” Brown and Atkins (1988) [9] state that lectures have been the most common form of teaching and learning since ancient times.

Majority of the teachers are of the view that it saves lots of time and our education system is syllabus and time bound. T₆ suggested, “Syllabus and time bounded so lecture method is also less time consuming and this also saves the problem of space due to more number of students.” Cannon (1988) [12] in the same vein says that although discussion methods in small groups appear to be a superior method of attaining higher-level intellectual learning, it is almost inevitable that the students will experience lectures, as the number of students attending is too large in comparison to the teaching staff available. Therefore, much emphasis in the past in the colleges and universities has been upon the lecture method.

Almost all the teachers prefer lecture method while some teachers who teach Science prefer demonstration method due to the nature of the subject which demanded touching, feeling and experimenting on their own. For instance, T₂ and T₉ conclude saying that our students get hands on experience through demonstration, they feel motivated and perform better.

Other striking reason for favoring lecture method is opined by T₆, “Teaching learning methods also reduces the use of teaching learning materials and when teaching materials are not available so we mostly go for lecture method.” Very few teachers use short field trip to make students learn related topic practically since it makes students learn through seeing in reality. For example, T₅ says, “Making short field trips to learn related topic practically really improves them and practically learn through the things that they see.” These are the few reasons among many, why teachers fancy lecture methods among many others.

B: Students’ Preference of teaching strategies

Students in general prefer their teachers to teach them with infusion of various teaching strategies with jokes in-between. One of the student participants says, “I prefer my teachers could give some important notes and explanation through practical” (S3). Beckman (1990) [3] affirms that students learn best when they are actively engaged in the

process. S6 further supports saying, "I prefer my teachers teaching with action and with good explanation for every sentence." S1, S5 and S6 desire their teachers to teach them with the use of various teaching strategies with the blend of jokes in-between teaching. They said this definitely make them learn, remember and understand better. Moody (1983)^[29], states that they must introduce variations into their lessons so that students are always kept alert and ready to respond to many different kinds of stimulus. In support of students' view and Moody, Osler (1899, cited in Nandi et.al, 2000)^[30] too is in favor of child-centered learning rather than lecture-based learning. In lecture method, teacher takes the lead role while students are the passive listener.

S6 opines bit differently, who mentions as

Teachers linking the lesson to the real life situation makes us gain knowledge of what is learn and understand more. Even presentation, expression and mood of the teacher who is teaching makes a lot of difference in learning. I prefer my teachers to teach in very attentive way, not in moody mood that made students to feel bored.

So teachers must possess all the skills, techniques, expressions, communication skills, understanding and many more including positive mood to be a perfect teacher and motivate our students to learn effectively. Probst (1984)^[31] asserts that the teaching atmosphere refers to the mood and flow of the classroom as the lesson begins and ends. This mood and flow, in effect, determines students' interest and concentration.

S2 has different things to say. The participant reports when teacher makes them to act in front of the class they learn topics by remembering the one who acted it out. While S3 favor teachers giving hints until they get the content and teaching is conducted through the integration of different teaching strategies like; discussion, experiment, conducting test, project work, giving notes and reading. So S3 supports the experiment based learning. Cooper and Associates (1990)^[14] confirm participant's view saying that students working in small group tend to learn more of what is taught and retain it longer than when the same content is presented in other instructional formats.

S6 has divergent opinion and states that teaching strategies does not matter much, what matters is the teachers going beyond the text book and exploring other means to provide additional information to the learners. Greeno (1997)^[25] states that students' ability to transfer information learned in a typical classroom setting to real life situations is sporadic and by chance. If learning is related, students learn better. Berns and Erickson (2001)^[4] further explain contextual teaching and learning as an innovative instructional process that helps students connect the content they are learning to the life contexts in which that content could be used.

So above mentioned strategies were some of the preferred teaching strategies that have been suggested by individual interviewees. The following section presents factors that affect the effective teaching in the classroom.

C: Factors affecting the Effective Teaching in the classroom: There are many factors that influence the effectiveness of teaching in the classroom. Many teachers have their own perspectives and students' view seem to contradict to the teachers.

Teacher's analysis of the factors affecting the effective teaching

Many teachers report that the factors affecting effective teaching to be illiterate parental back ground, environment that students' lives in, less classroom activities employed by teachers, availability of the teaching learning materials, students' interest for the subject, children's attitude towards the subject, proper guidance by the parents and finally the classroom conduciveness. Probst (1984)^[31] asserts that teaching atmosphere in the classroom should be in the non-threatening mode: conducive, non-competitive and thought-provoking thus allowing students to enjoy the lesson and learn better. One of the participants reported even students' receptivity too is very important. Allwright and Bailey (1991)^[1] confirm that although what happens in the class and teachers' effort is important but students' receptiveness is of paramount importance. According to teachers all these factors play important part in effective teaching and learning in the school.

Almost all teacher participants report the classroom conduciveness as the main factor and it mainly attributes to the large number of students in the classroom which makes it incapable for the teachers to move around and carryout activity. For example, T₄ affirms, "Factors are classroom spacious, classroom environment and for it group work is not possible." T₅ also mentions that, "Mainly having large teacher-student ratio." This factor is reiterated by T₉ saying, "Due to crowdedness we conduct less classroom activities." Further, T₇ has other reasons and stresses on the importance of correcting, checking and evaluating student's work after the completion of the work.

On the other hand, T₂ has different story and states that the main factor is examination system that we have in place, which actually makes our students easy going and spoils them. He further reiterates by saying that this type of examination system does not motivate our learners to learn and in the process it would create literate society not educated and learned society. The Self-Determination Theory developed by Deci and Ryan (1985)^[19], focuses on the importance of intrinsic motivation in driving human behavior. Our examination system minimizes the external pressure on our students by making it easy which would otherwise provide opportunity, redirect, motivate and alter the behavior of our learners to learn because of the pressure and perform as desired. These were the points suggested by teachers as the factors attributing to ineffective learning of our students.

Students' analysis on the factors affecting the effective teaching

Overwhelming majority of the student interviewees about six students made a reference to the teacher's inability to prepare lesson plans for teaching. As a result of it teachers are not able to perform as expected and it hampers the students' effective learning. S2 observed, "Our teachers do not have ready lesson plan." and S5 too has the same view who says, "They come without lesson plans." It is further supplemented by S6 saying, "Factors that affect the teacher's teaching is our teachers come to the class without preparing their lesson plan and just read from the text book."

On the other hand, few students' interviewees attribute to

lack of teaching learning materials available in the school as well as our teachers are not making use of those available too. Some say that teaching is affected by receptiveness and inattentiveness of the students who in turn mess up the mood of the teacher and disrupts the smooth flow of the teaching. Bailey (1991)^[1] confirms proposing that although what happens in the class and teachers' effort is important but students' receptiveness is of paramount importance. Other reasons reported are lack of supplementary information of the teachers besides the text book. S8 points out, "Teachers teach the students only from the text books where information is less."

On the contrary S7 has different and unique observation and it is the relationship of teachers and students and among themselves in the school. Eisner (2002)^[23] suggests that teaching is a caring exercise, while learning is an emotional exercise and is very much part of the effective learning process. S7 states, "Sometimes lack of cooperation with other teachers also affects the teacher's teaching but it is very rare." These are some of the reasons that students view for affecting effective learning and results in poor performance. The following section presents the impact of teaching strategies on motivation and how it raises the motivational level of our students.

D: Impact of Teaching Strategies on motivation to learn

As evidenced from the observation of the classroom teaching and the interviews of the teachers and the students, it reveals that our teachers use the same teaching strategies over and again resulting in monotony of interaction. As a result, the data suggest that students feel uninterested to study since there is no variation in teaching and feels as a burden to study. This consequently demotivates and causes ineffective learning in our students. Motivation to learning is usually associated with an eagerness to learn and a commitment to learning. Also students who are motivated to learn can be observed working thoroughly on the task, seeking understanding and persevering when they encounter challenges. Students are not motivated due to sameness and they become inattentive. Their learning becomes minimal (Hammond, 2003)^[26].

Using of the identical teaching strategies was not welcomed by the students. One of the student interviewees (S6) states that every time teaching in the same way is not good. Also knows that motivated learners feel encouraged, their eagerness increases and their curiosity too are increased. Similarly, Burden (2000)^[10] states that intrinsic motivation is a response to need that exists within the student such as curiosity, the need to know and feelings of competence or growth. To raise the motivational level, the data suggests the importance for teachers to modify teaching strategies and incorporate effective strategies while teaching. Schwartz and Pollishuke (1990)^[36] are against the teachers sticking to only one teaching strategy stating that teachers who consistently use only one teaching strategy have seriously limited the learning experiences of their learners. It is evident that the use of only one teaching strategy causes some hindrance in learning to our learners resulting in ineffective learning due to minimal motivation while teaching.

E: What motivates students to learn

There are ways and strategies which motivate our students to learn. Different learners learn differently and possess different intelligence. Educationists and Psychologists suggest the use of different teaching strategies that best suit different learners to maximize effective teaching-learning. The study interviewed students to explore their views on what motivates them to learn. S7 says that, "We get motivated when our teachers teach us in simple languages that are understandable to all of us and easy to memorize." The participant further says, "Some teachers show different body movement which make us laugh and make us more interesting to learn that particular topic."

On the other hand, S8, S6 and S3 have almost same views and said that they get motivated by teacher's teaching, expression they express while teaching, enforcing them to work, strictly checking their work, giving imposition, using simple language while teaching encouraging us and give equal opportunity. S6 affirms, "Joking, singing, asking question and demonstrating in front motivates us and makes us learn effectively."

Teachers and students have the same opinion. They feel that students must be encouraged to work by giving positive feedback such as: good, keep it up, well done and encouraging the weaker ones by paying more attention to them. For example, T₁ states, "We should appreciate the effort of the students saying words like: keep it up, good, well done and you can do it." This aligns with the intrinsic motivation as discussed earlier. Intrinsic motivation involves internal satisfaction that the students feel when performing the task. Salvin (1997)^[34] suggests that motivation is the influence of needs and desires on the intensity and the direction of behavior. The study found that when students feel cared for they prefer to persist further by putting extra effort.

Teachers in their training are given sufficient orientation with regard to award and reward and their relation to extrinsic motivation. Burden (2000)^[10] affirms that extrinsic motivation refers to motivation that comes from outside the learner and involves the delivery of external rewards after the completion of the task. Undertaking a given task may be motivated by promise of a prize or some other kind of gain which is external to the task. In the same vein Stipek (2002)^[39] states that for students to learn and derive maximum benefits from the school, educators must provide a learning context in which students are motivated to engage actively and productively in the activities.

Summary

This chapter basically discussed main themes and sub themes derived from the field interviews and observations. It also presented in some depth teaching strategies preferred by teachers that takes the Centre stage in the discussion. It fundamentally focuses on the teaching strategies that teachers employ and its impact on the effectiveness of teaching-learning process. Even it catered to some of the reasons for not being able to teach, from both teachers and students' perspective. Next chapter presents the findings and the recommendations of the study.

Chapter Five

Findings and Recommendations

Introduction

This chapter presents findings and recommendations on Impact teaching strategies that teachers employ on students' level of motivation to learn effectively in three schools under Mongar Dzongkhag. Findings of the research have been organized and discussed in detail under different headings as follows: 1/ Teaching strategies that are in use, 2/ Preference of teaching strategies, 3/ Factors affecting the effective teaching, 4/ Impact of teaching strategies on students' motivation.

Findings

Teaching Strategies that are in use

The study confirmed that teachers in the school do not employ varied teaching strategies in teaching learning process. Among many teaching strategies present in the world of teaching, our teachers mostly prefer lecture method, then followed by demonstration, chalk and talk method and question-answer method. Teacher interviewees reported that they favor lecture method. Similarly, a large majority of the student respondents propounded that their teachers usually use lecture method in the classroom teaching. By the same token, it was evident from the classroom teaching observation carried out for three teachers.

Preference of Teaching Strategies

Preferences of teaching strategies are categorized differently under two-sub headings: 1/ Teacher's preference of teaching strategies and 2/ Student's preference of teaching strategies.

Teacher's preference of teaching strategies

Data collected revealed that a large majority of teacher participants prefer lecture method over others. The reasons propounded were due to the nature of the subject, teachers are of the view that it saves time, large number of students in the class and small size of the classrooms. These reasons attribute to the use of lecture method and prove to be the best strategy in Bhutanese Education context.

Student's Preference of teaching strategies

Study conducted exposed that students in general have a preference for the use of various teaching strategies (especially discussion and experiment based learning) in the teaching learning process with the blend of jokes in between teaching lesson. The study revealed that student interviewees are also in favor of teachers linking real life situation with the knowledge they learn in the classroom makes them learn and remember more. Student participants are also in favor of teachers exploring more on the subject besides the text books.

Factors affecting the effective teaching in the classroom

Overwhelming majority of the teachers: five out of six reported that factors affecting the effective teaching are due to illiterate parents unable to guide their children, lack of teaching learning materials and lack of conducive classroom environment due to large number of students. On the other hand, student interviewees made reference to teacher's inability to prepare teaching lesson plans, lack of teaching

learning materials, inattentiveness of the students, lack of supplementary information besides text books and relation among teachers are the factors affecting the effective teaching in the class. These are the factors that affect the effective teaching in the school.

Impact of teaching strategies on motivation

It is evident from observation of classroom teaching that there is lack of student's motivation. Our teachers use the same teaching strategies for teaching and that makes our learners uninterested, learning becomes burden resulting in ineffective learning. Students in unmotivated classroom exhibit behavior like: inattentive, agitated, sleepy, bored, yawned, talked to each other and are not interested in the lesson. From this we can draw conclusion that teaching strategies our teachers employ in teaching have immense impact on student's motivation to learn effectively.

Recommendations

On the basis of data collected from the field through interviews and observation, analysis of data and findings, following recommendation are being offered.

Ministry of Education and Skill Development

1. There is a need for the ministry to negotiate with the College of Education to look into the possibility of offering courses on motivation compulsorily to all the teacher trainees in the two Colleges of Education.
2. Ministry could redesign the courses offered at the two Colleges of Education basically focusing on the teaching strategies with child centered learning.

Dzongkhag Education Sector

Dzongkhag Education Sector could explore the means to provide all the teaching-learning related materials to the schools.

School Management

1. School Management could provide professional developmental and support to the teachers by exploring the means.
2. School authority could evaluate the performance of the teachers through monitoring the process of teaching including checking of all plans, preparation of teaching learning materials and teaching with the infusion of child-centered learning strategies.

Conclusion

This study mainly discussed on Impact of teaching strategies that teachers employ on students' level of motivation to learn effectively. It basically focused on relationship between teaching strategies and motivation. Our teachers among many other teaching methods present generally use lecture method to teach our students and that makes our learners uninterested, resulting in minimal learning and demotivating.

This study revealed the rationale for our teachers in the field for preferring the lecture method over other methods. Overwhelming majority of teacher participants reported that use of this method is owing to over flooding of small classroom with students and also attributes to the lack of teaching learning materials in the school. Study also found the factors

that affect the effective learning of our students as well as the rationale for teachers not being able to perform better in the classroom teaching.

This study was a venture to discover the relation between the teaching strategies that teachers take up for teaching our students and its impact on motivation; their correlation. It also looked at the factors that affect effective teaching learning process in the school. After having explored the factors affecting effective teaching-learning process, researcher is hopeful that the concern agency would look into this matter diligently. Still hopeful that the recommendations recommended would be considered favorably so that our future leaders of Bhutan get the best out of it.

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